

The Effect of Information Quality, System Quality and Organizational Capability on the Implementation of HMIS at Regional public hospital Pambalah Batung, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency

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ABSTRACT: The Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) is an integral part of overall hospital services and has even become one of the main joints in daily activities. Evaluation of HMIS implementation is carried out because it will assess the benefits derived from HMIS implementation and find potential problems faced by users and organizations. The results of this evaluation can be used as a reference for improving or perfecting the HMIS and minimizing the potential for existing problems, so that HMIS becomes better, perfect and can support the vision, mission and goals of the organization. The find out the quality of information, system quality and organizational capabilities in implementing HMIS at Pambalah Batung Hospital. This research is an associative research with a quantitative paradigm. The sample in this research is 150 respondents. The data analysis technique used a simple and multiple linear regression analysis test. There is an influence between information quality ($p=0.000$), system quality ($p=0.000$) and organizational capability ($p=0.000$) on HMIS implementation. Information quality, system quality and organizational capability simultaneously influence HMIS implementation ($p=0.000$). Information quality is the most dominant in HMIS implementation with a constant value ($b = 0.387$) (4.680). There is influence between information quality, system quality and organizational capability partially and simultaneously on HMIS implementation. Information quality has a dominant significant effect on HMIS implementation at Pambalah Batung Hospital. Pambalah Batung Amuntai Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, further improves the information system for HMIS employees and must pay more attention to information systems by always improving good information systems and also providing information to Pambalah Batung Hospital.

KEYWORDS: Hospital Management Information Systems, Information, Organizational Capabilities, Systems.

INTRODUCTION

The crucial role of the health sector in establishing accountability is evident through the development of an appropriate accountability system. The focus lies in health development by reinforcing primary healthcare efforts, improving health insurance, enhancing service accessibility, and implementing Health Information Systems (HIS). Hospitals are expected to enhance service quality through the Health Information System (HIS). In the era of globalization, information and communication technology, especially Hospital Management Information Systems (HMIS), becomes pivotal in improving healthcare efficiency and effectiveness (Almunawar et al, 2012). An evaluation of the HMIS at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital revealed several issues, including information quality, system utilization, and organizational aspects (Balaraman et al, 2013).

Health development policies emphasize strengthening primary healthcare, health insurance, and enhancing service accessibility and quality. Hospitals, as the primary healthcare providers, face demands to improve service quality and accessibility, with strong support from the Health Information System (HIS). The introduction of information technology in the health sector is a global phenomenon, with a focus on the quality of generated information. Health organizations are expected to understand and manage information technology effectively to enhance performance. In this context, the Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) is crucial for administrative efficiency. The evaluation of HMIS, especially at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, is essential to identify issues related to information quality, system characteristics, and deficiencies in human resource management. Particularly in terms of information quality, Information Systems, and organizational capabilities. Several challenges, such as non-compliance with Health Minister Regulation 83, characteristics of a closed-source system, and a lack of human resources and responsible installations, need to be addressed for HMIS optimization.

Based on the background described above, the problem formulations that can be derived are:

1. Does Information Quality, Information System, and Organizational Capability have a significant simultaneous effect on the Implementation of Hospital Information Management System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency?
2. Does Information Quality, Information System, and Organizational Capability have a significant partial effect on the Implementation of HMIS at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency?
3. Which among Information Quality, Information System, and Organizational Capability has a dominant influence on the Implementation of HMIS at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Health Management

Health factors are considered one of the fundamental human rights, as stated in the 1945 Constitution of Indonesia. The constitution emphasizes that every individual has the right to live prosperously in both body and soul, reside in a good and healthy environment, and receive healthcare services. Viewing health as a fundamental human right entails an obligation to provide care for the sick and strive to maintain the well-being of those who are healthy. Health is defined as the state of well-being encompassing physical, mental, and social aspects that enables individuals to live socially and economically productive lives. This foundational concept supports the idea that good health is an investment.

Notoatmodjo (2013:14) highlights the importance of developing health management in various health organizations in Indonesia, including the Ministry of Health, Regional Health Offices, Hospitals, Community Health Centers, and their respective branches. To comprehend the implementation of health management in hospitals, health offices, and Community Health centers, a study of the annual planning processes of the Ministry of Health and Regional Health Offices is necessary. Specifically for Community Health centers, management practices can be examined through the five-year planning process (micro-planning), task distribution, and job descriptions of Community Health centers staff according to their respective roles. Munir (2011: 17) defines health management as "an activity or an art of organizing healthcare and non-healthcare personnel to improve public health through health programs." In other words, public health management is the application of general management principles within the public healthcare system, with the focus on the health service system for the community. Darwis (2011:45) health management is the application of general management in the public health service system so that the object or target of management is the public health service system.

Health management needs to be developed in every health organization in Indonesia such as the Ministry of Health Office, regional Health Services, Hospitals and Community Health Centers and their staff. To understand the implementation of health management in hospitals, health services and community health centers, it is necessary to study the process of preparing annual plans for the Ministry of Health and regional health services. Especially at the Community Health centers level, the implementation of management can be studied through plans prepared every five years (micro planning), the division and description of the duties of Community Health centers staff according to their respective main tasks.

b. Information System

Law Number 14 of 2008 concerning Public Information Transparency explains that the right to obtain public information is a fundamental right of citizens that must be protected by law. Public bodies are obliged to implement a good information system to effectively deliver public information through both electronic and non-electronic media. This law encourages public bodies, including local governments, to disclose information reasonably known to the public (Puspita and Martani, 2011). DeLone & McLean (1992) as cited in Wirautama (2011) explain that the quality of information systems must meet reliability standards to satisfy users. User behavior regarding information systems will influence technology usage. Information quality is related to system use, user satisfaction, and net benefits (DeLone and McLean 1992, 2003). Information quality has attributes such as information obtained from a system, accuracy of information, relevance of information, timeliness, and completeness of information. Information quality often constitutes a key dimension concerning end-user satisfaction instruments (Ives et al., 1983; Baroudi and Orlikowski, 1988; Doll et al., 1994). As a result, information quality is often not distinguished as a unique construct but measured as a component of user satisfaction.

In processing, a system will ultimately produce information. For this reason, the quality of information is very necessary to support

the successful development of the system to be designed. Indicators of information quality according to DeLone and McLean (2003) in Rachmawati (2012) include:

1. Flexibility: An information system shows that the information system implemented has good quality. The flexibility in question is the system's capabilities information in making changes related to meeting user needs.
2. Ease of Use (Easy of Use) An information system can be said to be of quality if the system is designed to meet user satisfaction through ease of use of the information system.
3. System Reliability (Realibility) A quality information system is an information system that can be relied upon. If the system is reliable then the information system is suitable for use. Information system reliability in this context is the resilience of the information system from damage and errors

c. *System Quality*

System quality is a measurement of the information system process that focuses on the outcomes of interaction between users and the system. System quality encompasses attributes such as equipment availability, equipment reliability, ease of use, and response time, which are determining factors for whether an information system is utilized or not. Nielsen (2000) argues that there are several usability principles in the online environment, namely navigation, response time, credibility, and content. From various literature, it is evident that there are four dimensions of system quality: navigation, ease of use, response time, and security. McKinney et al. (2002) propose three dimensions of system quality: access, usability, and navigation.

System quality can be measured by examining its functional aspect, known as usability. Usability is a crucial part of the human-computer interaction principle, providing essential guidelines for learning design. Nielsen (2000) suggests that usability comprises four basic principles in online activities: navigation, timelines, credibility, and content. Palmer (2002) states that key elements in website usage include consistency, ease of use, clarity of interaction, readability, information arrangement, speed, and website layout/design.

According to Jogiyanto (2007:15), information quality measures the quality of the output from the information system. Ong et al. (2009:399) argue that information quality can be interpreted as measuring the content quality of the information system. Negash et al. (2003:758) explain that Information Quality is a function related to the value of the information output generated by the system. Based on various expert opinions, it can be concluded that information quality is a measurement focused on the output produced by the system and the value of that output for users. According to Jogiyanto (2005:10), indicators of information quality include:

1. Accurate, information must be free from errors and not biased or misleading. Information must have certain accuracy so that there is no doubt about its truth.
2. On time, information that comes to the recipient must not arrive late, because information that does not arrive on time is no longer valuable, because the information is used in the decision-making process.
3. Relevant, information has useful value according to what is needed by the user. Information has different levels of relativity, depending on the level of user.

d. *Organizational Capabilities*

Organizational capability is a concept used to refer to the internal environmental conditions comprising two strategic factors: strengths and weaknesses. Strengths are positive internal situations and capabilities that enable the organization to have a strategic advantage in achieving its objectives, while weaknesses are internal situations and incapacities that prevent the organization from achieving its goals (Higgins in Salusu, 2005:391). Organizational capability does not represent a single resource alone without reference to other resources, such as financial assets, technology, or workforce, but rather is a distinctive and superior way of allocating resources (Schreyogg in Kusumasari, 2014:45). According to these experts, organizational capability is crucial for integrating and exploring resources within an organization to achieve its desired goals, encompassing human resources, financial resources, institutional resources, and others. Organizational capability cannot be created with only one resource; it requires the support of other resources. Organizational capability is significant because it is identified as one of the primary sources for generating and developing competitiveness. The uncertainty and environmental changes necessitate organizational capabilities for organizations to adapt and rapidly develop prerequisites to sustain competitive advantages (Schreyog and Kliesch-Eberl in Kusumasari, 2014:43).

Organizational capability is determined based on two approaches: the functional approach and the value chain approach according to Hubeis and Najib (2014:47). The functional approach determines organizational capability relative to the company's main functions, such as marketing, distribution, finance and accounting, human resources, production, and organization in general. The value chain approach determines organizational capability based on a series of sequential activities that constitute a set of value activities performed to design, produce, market, deliver, and support products and services.

Sampurno (2011:55) emphasizes the importance of distinguishing between resources and organizational capabilities, where resources are productive assets owned by the company, while capabilities are what the company can do. A single resource does not carry much meaning in competitive advantage; rather, they must collaborate to create organizational capabilities. Building and sustaining resources and organizational capabilities require two conditions: scarcity and relevance. If resources or capabilities are widely available in the industry, it may be essential to compete but not sufficient as a basis for a competitive advantage. Profits derived from resources and capabilities depend not only on the company's ability to build an advantage but also on how long that advantage can be sustained, depending on how enduring the resources and capabilities are.

e. Hospital Management Information System (HMIS)

Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) is an information communication technology system that processes and integrates the entire workflow of hospital services in the form of a coordinated network, reporting, and administrative procedures to obtain accurate and timely information. It is a part of the Health Information System (Ministry of Health, Republic of Indonesia, 2013). According to Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 82, Article 4, Year 2013, regarding the hospital management information system, institutions are obliged; every hospital must implement the management and development of HMIS. The implementation of the management and development of HMIS as mentioned in paragraph (1) must be able to improve and support the healthcare process in the hospital, including speed, accuracy, integration, service improvement, efficiency improvement, ease of reporting in operational implementation, speed of decision-making, accuracy, speed of problem identification, and ease of strategy development in managerial implementation, work culture, transparency, coordination between units, system understanding, and reduction of administrative costs in organizational implementation.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the definition of Assessment (evaluation) is a systematic way to study based on experience and use the lessons learned to improve ongoing activities and enhance better planning with careful selection for the future (Wijono, 1999). According to the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 44 of 2009, a hospital is a healthcare institution for the public with its own characteristics influenced by the development of health science, technological advances, and the socio-economic life of the community. It must be able to continuously improve quality services that are accessible to the public to achieve the highest possible degree of health. The definition of the Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) is a communication technology system that processes and integrates the entire workflow of hospital services in the form of a coordinated network, reporting, and administrative procedures to obtain accurate and timely information. It is part of the Health Information System (Ministry of Health, Republic of Indonesia, 2013).

In the implementation of HMIS, the patient admission area is the first service gateway in a healthcare facility. Some patients decide to seek treatment at a healthcare facility by considering a comfortable patient admission area and satisfactory staff. The registration process serves various interests, including the immediate use of registration data for individual identification, the implementation of evaluation and services for patients (Budi, 2011). To enhance HMIS performance, an evaluation is needed for the existing system to identify positive aspects that encourage system usage and identify factors causing obstacles. Evaluation covers various aspects of the use of information and communication technology in hospitals. Some studies indicate that the trend in health information system evaluations not only considers technological aspects but also takes into account human and organizational aspects. Through this evaluation, hospitals can develop HMIS by considering user needs and factors that influence HMIS usage and expected benefits. The objectives of this paper are to evaluate the system quality and service quality of the hospital management information system in the outpatient registration section, evaluate the system quality and service quality of the hospital management information system in the outpatient registration section towards the organization, evaluate the staff (human) and organization regarding the benefits of the hospital management information system in the outpatient registration section, and understand the benefits of the hospital management information system in the outpatient registration section.

f. Hypothesis

The hypothesis proposed in this research is:

- H1 : Quality of Information, System Quality, and Organizational Capability have a significant partial influence on the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at the Regional General Hospital Pambalah Batung, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.
- H2 : Quality of Information, System Quality, and Organizational Capability jointly and significantly influence the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at the Regional General Hospital Pambalah Batung, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.
- H3 : Organizational Capability has a dominant influence on the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at the Regional General Hospital Pambalah Batung, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

g. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

This study, based on the type of data, is an associative research with a quantitative paradigm. The aim is to determine the relationship between two or more variables using numerical data. The form of variable relationships in this study is in the form of a causal relationship (cause and effect), as indicated by the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. The purpose of this research is to obtain an evaluation and clarity of the relationships between variables using statistical calculations or explanatory research. The population for this study consists of personnel/users in Pambalah Batung Amuntai Regional General Hospital totaling 150 individuals or an average daily population collection of 30 individuals over 5 days. The sample size for this study is determined as 150 respondents or 20% - 25% of the population, selected as the sample. Data analysis is conducted based on primary data obtained directly through the distribution of questionnaires to patients, which will then be analyzed using multiple regression analysis with the assistance of the SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) Version 17 for Windows program. Data collection techniques use literature study, observation, interviews, documentation and questionnaires, then the data uses multiple regression analysis. To test the hypothesis, it is carried out using the Instrument Validity and Reliability Test and the Classical Assumption test

Variable Operational Definition

1. Information Quality (X1) relates to system use, user satisfaction and net benefits with indicators of Flexibility, Easy of Use and Reliability
2. Information Quality (X2) is a measurement of information system processes that focuses on the results of interactions between users and systems with indicators of Accuracy, Timeliness and Relevance.

3. Organizational Capability (X3) is a concept used to refer to internal environmental conditions which consist of two strategic factors, namely strengths and weaknesses with indicators of skills or expertise, valuable physical assets, human resource assets, valuable organizational assets, competitive capabilities and Alliances and cooperation
4. Implementation of HMIS (Y) is a Hospital Management Information System which is a communication information technology system that processes and integrates the entire flow of hospital service processes in the form of a network of coordination, reporting and administrative procedures to obtain precise and accurate information using Technology, Human and Organizational indicators. and Benefits

RESULT

Validity Test

Table 1. The Result of Validity Test

Variabel	Item	R Count	Keterangan
Information System (X1)	X1.1	0,836	Valid
	X1.2	0,674	Valid
	X1.3	0,789	Valid
	X1.4	0,905	Valid
Quality of information systems (X2)	X2.1	0,865	Valid
	X2.2	0,896	Valid
	X2.3	0,782	Valid
	X2.4	0,917	Valid
	X2.5	0,860	Valid
Organizational Capabilities (X3)	X3.1	0,666	Valid
	X3.2	0,700	Valid
	X3.3	0,832	Valid
	X3.4	0,711	Valid
	X3.5	0,526	Valid
	X3.6	0,608	Valid
	X3.7	0,856	Valid
HMIS (Y)	Y1	0,801	Valid
	Y2	0,696	Valid
	Y3	0,854	Valid
	Y4	0,797	Valid

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the validity test in Table 1 above, in the validity test, all questionnaire items are declared valid because all questionnaire items have correlation values greater than the required r value of 0.3.

Reliability Test

Table 2. The Result of Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Description
1	Information System (X1)	0,808	Reliable
2	Quality of information systems (X2)	0,906	Reliable
3	Organizational Capabilities (X3)	0,828	Reliable
4	HMIS (Y)	0,793	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on the results of the reliability test in this study, the reliability value of all instruments is accepted or reliable because it has a minimum Cronbach's Alpha and Cronbach's Alpha If Item Deleted values greater than the reliability standard, which is 0.6.

Multiple Linear Regression

The testing was conducted with a confidence level of 95% or a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). To examine the validity of these hypotheses, multiple linear regression analysis was employed. In this regression analysis, both simultaneous or F-test and partial or t-test will be conducted.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.608	.940		4.903	.000
X1	.387	.076	.433	5.090	.000
X2	.055	.075	7.07	7.320	.000
X3	.166	.052	.306	3.191	.002

Source: Primary data processed.

According to Table 3, the regression equation is as follows: $Y = 4,608 + 0,387X_1 + 0,055X_2 + 0,166X_3$

1. a = Constant value of 4.608, meaning that if the values of information system, information quality, and organizational capability variables are zero (0), then the performance will increase by 4.608 units.
2. b1 = Coefficient value of X1 is 0.387, indicating that each one-unit increase in information quality (X1) results in a 0.387-unit increase in the HMIS variable, assuming that the other variables consisting of information quality (X2) and organizational capability (X3) are constant or fixed.
3. b2 = Coefficient value of X2 is 0.055, indicating that each one-unit increase in the information system variable (X2) results in a 0.055-unit increase in the HMIS variable, assuming that the other variables consisting of information quality (X1) and organizational capability (X3) are constant or fixed.
4. b3 = Coefficient value of X3 is 0.166, indicating that each one-unit increase in the drug management variable (X2) results in a 0.166-unit increase in the HMIS variable, assuming that the other variables consisting of information quality (X1) and information system (X2) are constant or fixed.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 4. Simultaneous Test

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	297.857	3	99.286	60.169	.000 ^b
	Residual	240.917	146	1.650		
	Total	538.773	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

Uji F

Based on Table 4, the calculated F value of 60.169 > F table 2.67 shows a positive direction and has a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that simultaneously Information Quality, System Quality and Organizational Capability have a positive

and significant effect on HMIS Implementation at Regional General Hospitals. Pambalah Batung, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

t-Test

Based on the table 3, the t test results can be explained as follows:

1. The Influence of Information Quality on the Implementation of HMIS at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, the calculated t value is 5,090 > t table 1.976 shows a positive direction and has a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that Information Quality has a positive and significant effect on HMIS Implementation at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.
2. The influence of the quality of the information system on the implementation of HMIS at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, the calculated t value is 7,320 > t table 1.976 shows a positive direction and has a significance value of 0.000 > 0.05 so it can be concluded that the quality of the information system has a positive and significant effect. towards the Implementation of HMIS at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.
3. The Influence of Organizational Capability on the Implementation of HMIS at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, the calculated t value is 3,191 > t table 1.976 indicating a positive direction and has a significance value of 0.002 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that Organizational Capability has a positive and significant effect on HMIS Implementation at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

Dominance Test (Beta Coefficient Testing)

Based on Table 3, the Beta value for the Information Quality Variable is 0.127; System quality 0.281; Organizational Capability is 0.321, so it can be concluded that the system quality variable has a dominant influence on the implementation of SIMRS at the Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

Table 4. Test the Coefficient Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.744 ^a	.553	.544	1.285

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

Based on the output in SPSS above, the Adjusted R2 value is 0.544. This means that the information quality variable (X1), the information system variable (X2) and the organizational capability variable (X3) are able to explain 54.4% of the variation in the dependent variable, namely the Implementation of the Pambalah Batung Hospital Management Information System, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency. This shows that the combined contribution of the three independent variables is 54.4%, while the remaining 45.6% is caused by other factors that were not included or detected in this study.

DISCUSSION

The Information Quality, System Quality, and Organizational Capability simultaneously influence the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

From the ANOVA table (see Appendix), the obtained Sig value (0.000) is less than α (0.005), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H0). The ANOVA table also provides the F-value of 60.169, and from the table, the critical F-value (F_{table}) is 2.67. As the calculated F-value (F_{hitung}) is greater than the critical F-value (F_{table}), H0 is rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that all three variables significantly influence the Hospital Information Management System (HMIS).

The Information Quality, System Quality, and Organizational Capability partially influence the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

The correlation between information quality and hospital management information system (HMIS) is moderate and positive (refer to the Parametric Statistics book by Sofyan Siregar in the Correlation chapter), with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.703. The better

the information system, the better the hospital management information system.

The correlation between system quality and hospital management information system (HMIS) is moderate and positive (refer to the Parametric Statistics book by Sofyan Siregar in the Correlation chapter), with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.620. Better system quality corresponds to a better hospital management information system. System quality is a measurement of the information system process that focuses on the outcomes of interaction between users and the system. System quality attributes include equipment availability, equipment reliability, ease of use, and response time, which are determining factors for the adoption or rejection of an information system. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is an influence of system quality on the hospital management information system (HMIS).

The correlation between organizational capability and hospital management information system (HMIS) is moderate and positive (refer to the Parametric Statistics book by Sofyan Siregar in the Correlation chapter), with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.671. The better the organizational capability, the better the hospital management information system. Organizational capability refers to the concept used to indicate the internal environmental conditions consisting of two strategic factors, namely strengths and weaknesses.

Information Quality, System Quality, and Organizational Capability that dominantly influence the Implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

Based on the data processing results, the System Information variable (X_1) is identified as the dominant variable affecting the Hospital Management Information System (HMIS) variable (Y), with an impact percentage of 30.477%. In the test of dominance in the research, it can be stated that the System Information Quality dominantly influences the Implementation of HMIS at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Hulu Sungai Utara Regency.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Information Quality, Information System, and Organizational Capability significantly influence the implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) simultaneously at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Amuntai, South Kalimantan Province.
2. Information Quality, Information System, and Organizational Capability have a significant partial impact on the implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Amuntai, South Kalimantan Province.
3. Information System has a significant and dominant influence on the implementation of Hospital Information System (HMIS) at Pambalah Batung Regional General Hospital in Amuntai, South Kalimantan Province.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions, the recommendations from the results of this research are:

1. Regional Public Hospital Pambalah Batung in Amuntai, Hulu Sungai Utara Regency, should further enhance the information system for HMIS employees and pay closer attention to the information system by continually improving a good Information System. Additionally, it should provide information to Pambalah Batung Amuntai Regional General Hospital in South Kalimantan Province.
2. It is expected that this will broaden the knowledge insights for postgraduate students in the field of Health Management Master's Program and serve as additional literature for Pancasetia Banjarmasin College of Economics.
3. For future researchers, it is advisable to add more independent variables to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing Employee Performance. This can be used as a reference for analyzing the quality of information, information systems, and organizational factors that dominantly influence the implementation of HMIS in hospitals.

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